

Emergence of the *SŪsanamaãâine Pariyatti PŪli* University in Bago

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Abstract

The Maãâine Pariyatti PŪli University was founded led by the Ven.PaããŪjota in 1319 ME. The Venerables of this monastery are PŪli PŪragPs, DhammŪcariyas, Pathamagyis, Pathamalats and Pathamangwes. Therefore this monastery became PŪli University in 1321 ME (1.3.1959). This University has held the Vinaya recitation since 1341 ME as recognized department of Vinaya recitation allowed by the Center of Shwekyin NikŪya Sayadawgyis. Since 1339 ME, 10 days MahŪsatipaããhŪna meditation center has opened for all monks residing in this University. The courses for Pathamapyan and DhammŪcariya have been taught specifically. There have qualified teachers always for filling the needs in education. The donors are supporting the four requisites. So the University becomes developed to be able to celebrate the golden jubilee in the year 2551 BE, 1369 ME, 2007 AD. It is 59 years old now that this monestry has been built.

Introduction

The *SŪsanamaãâine Pariyatti PŪli* University is a great religious centre for the young monks. The abbot and all responsible sayadaws take their responsibilities not only to educate the pupils but also to nurture them to become all round perfect ones. According to its name, the *SŪsanamaãâine* University is a religious centre which produces the educated monks.

The *SŪsanamaãâine Pariyatti PŪli* University stands in Panchankone of Bago City. It was established on the Wednesday, the fullmoon day of Nayon, 1319 ME (12.6.1957) with the 37 rains-retreats resident monks. It was upgraded to the level of University on the 7th waxing of Tapotwe, 1320 ME (1.3.1959). The founder was the Venerable PaããŪjota (*AggamahŪpaããita*). In 1344 ME (1983), it could celebrate the Silver Jubilee because it was exactly 25 years. In 1369 ME (2007) it was 50 years to get the chance to celebrate the Golden Jubilee.

The *SŪsanamaãâine* University is one of the famous learning center in Bago city. In the lower Myanmar, the Kingdom of Mon, Buddhism flourished after Bagan. Wareru, a Shan adventurer made himself the ruler in Martaban. Under him, Mon monasteries flourished and Mon monks compiled a code of law based on ancient Hindu codes of law. According to the statements in the *JinakŪlamŪiŪ*, the *SŪsanavaãsa* and the KalyŪnŪ inscriptions indicated that at that time close religious ties existed between the Buddhist Saãghas of Myanmar and ¼rŪlaBkŪ.

King *DhammacetŪ* (1472-92) took a special place in the history of the religion in Myanmar. He unified the *Saãgha* in the Mon Country and purified the Buddhist Order of the monks. He recorded his great service to the country in the *KalyŪnŪ* inscription.

DhammacetŪ was a Mon monk who helped the Mon queen ShinSawpu back to Bago. Afterwards *DhammacetŪ* was handed the throne. *DhammacetŪ* saw the future of Buddhism so that to change the *Saãgha* for the better. He sent 22 senior monks

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with their 22 disciples to 𑄎𑄢𑄣𑄤𑄥. They received the ordination from the 𑄎𑄢𑄣𑄤𑄥 *MahÜtheras* in the Chapter hall of *KalyÜnÝ* river. When they returned, King *DhammacetÝ* established *KalyÜnÝ* chapter hall and he made ordinations. According to *KalyÜnÝ* inscription, the number of 15666 ordinations is recorded. Therefore as a tradition, Bago city becomes a center of Buddhism. (SÜsanÜvamsakkamavibhÜvanÝ. 105-118.)

So also the *SÜsanamaãâine* University is housed as a eminent monastery on the sacred ground of Bago city. It can pass on the *Pariyatti*, *Paáipatti* and *Paáiveda* *SÜsanÜ* to the next generations. Because of the effort of the Venerable *NÜyaka* Sayadaw and his followers, they can carry the torch of Buddhism to the 25th Silver jubilee and 50th Golden jubilee.

Here to appreciate is the name of the University “*SÜsanamaãâine*”. It can be divided into two words *SÜsana* + *maãâine*. *SÜsana* has three aspects: *Pariyatti*-doctrinal, *Paáipatti*- practical and *Paáiveda*- realizable. *Maãâine* comes from *maãâana* which means decoration or adornment. If it is taken this meaning, the *SÜsanamaãâine* is the University which adorns the learners or monks lived in it with this three Teachings of the Lord Buddha. This is the first meaning. And for the second meaning, it should be assumed from *maãâala*- the circle surface of the three Teachings of the Lord Buddha. According to the Moneywe *Jetavana* Sayadaw and Kinwunmingyi suggested that this *maãâine* was a pure Myanmar word. So they spelled it ‘mantine’ and translated it ‘centre’. Therefore the meaning should be taken as the centre of the three Teachings of the Lord Buddha. In fact this *SÜsanamaãâine* is named according to the sense (*anvattha*).

In addition, this *SÜsanamaãâine* University is not only situated in Bago city but also at the eastern face around the historical *Haãsa* mount of pagoda. All resident monks have to follow the principles respectfully not only the *Vinaya* rules but also gang rules laid down. The Venerable *NÜyaka* Sayadaw made the learners meditate the insight meditation for ten days after their examination. They could not get the chance for travelling without this ten-day meditation practice. If they were devoted to that practice, he sent them to *MahÜsi SÜsana* Centre.

The most important work of the *SÜsanamaãâine* is the ceremony of *Vinaya* recital. Bago city should be named “*Vinaya city*” because Phonetawgyi U *SÝla* propagated Buddhism in Bago. It was called *AraãavÜsÝ* gang (Forest Sect). When *Ádikammika* Shwekyin Sayadaw met with U *SÝla*, Shwekyin Sect and Forest Sect assembled in 1244 ME (1975). In 1341 ME (1978), according to the decision of the State *Saãgha* Organization that was there could be opened a *Vinaya* recital centre if there were at least 30 monks and total 150 of monks and novices. So the *Vinaya* recital was first held in 1341 ME (1978) including 9 monasteries with 520 monks. In 1350 ME (1988) after one decade, it included 24 monasteries with 746 monks. In 1360 ME (1998), after the second decade, there included 34 monasteries with 888 monks. In 1365 ME (2003), in the 25th year, the Silver jubilee ceremony, there progressed upto 40 monasteries and 1116 monks.

Vinaya is the most important in the Teachings of the Buddha. “*Vinayo nÜma SÜsanassa Áyu, vinaye áhite SÜsanaã áhitaã hoti*” (*Vin, A, I, 11.*) -*Vinaya* is the life of the *SÜsana*. As long as *Vinaya* exists, that *SÜsanÜ* will exist too. And the Lord Buddha said the Last words to the Venerable *Ánanda*. Among them He said that after His *parinibbÜna*, the *Dhamma* and *Vinaya* would be the Teacher of the *Saãgha*. Therefore it is to say that the *SÜsanamaãâine* University contributes to the

development of Buddhism. It is taking the role in the propagation and prosperity of Buddhism.

Now it is going to present the emergence of the University

Emergence of the *SÜsanamaãâine PÜli* University in Bago

Here, the emergence of the *SÜsanamaãâine PÜli* University is mentioned from the article “25 years old *SÜsanamaãâine*” (SJJ, 29.) written by the *Maãâine Sayadaw*, the Ven. U *PaààÜjota* in the Silver Jubilee Journal published in January, 1983.

The Foundation of the *SÜsanamaãâine* University

The *SÜsanamaãâine* University was founded on the Wednesday, the fullmoon of Nayon, 1319 ME (12.6.1957). The University founder Sayadaw was a native of Moneywar. He wanted to build a university in Moneywar just like a university *PajjotÜrÜma* in Myangmya. (SJJ, 29.) However the Ven. *PaààÜvÜ* (half-uncle) from the *MahÜsÝsÜsana* Centre, Bago encouraged him to build a *Pariyatti* monastery in Bago as he wanted to support the *PariyattisÜsanÜ*. (Ibid, 30.) He discussed with other Sayadawgyis who had the same idea. So he decided to build the monastery in Bago. Then he went to India and Ceylon to go on pilgrimage. He made a programme to built the monastery after he had come back from the pilgrimage. While he was staying for his rains-retreat at the Bago Meditation Centre, he had to give lectures according to the order of the Ven. *SÝÜcÜra* of the monastery, *PadhÜnikÜrÜma*. So he was again encouraged to continue the teaching. But he rejected it and also the entrusting of the monastery by the Ven. *Cwetawshaung Sayadaw* near *Shwemawdaw* pagoda. (Ibid) The donors *Daw Yin*, *Daw Nyo* and *Daw Hnin Mya*, a group of sister donated him an acre of Land. So it was decided to found a monastery on that land after he had returned from the pilgrimage.

Since the month *Tapotwe*, 1318 ME (February, 1957) the land for the monastery was clean and *parittas* were recited and shared loving-kindness. There the Ven. *Ngwetaung Sayadawgyi*, the Ven. *Sayadaw* of Bago Meditation Centre and the Ven. *Indriya* of Meditation centre supported.

Rain-retreat by the 37 monks (SJJ, 31.)

On the Wednesday in the month of fullmoon day of Nayon, 1319 ME (12.6.1957), as the building were built to some extent, the 37 monks transferred to this *SÜsanamaãâine* monastery from the meditation centre and there they observed their rains-retreat. In this rain-retreat, the Ven. U *Saãvara*, incharge monk, U *PaààÜsÝha*, U *SÝhaàÜãa*, U *NÜgavaãsa*, U *Agginda*, U *Sobhita*, U *IndÜcakka* and U *Paããita* etc who had arrived since the monastery was built.

They kept in their mind that there could some cases be happened in the new monastery or houses (*navÜvÜso bahukicco*) (Ud, 148.) so they decided their mind to work and teach at the same time in the first two years, there appeared three *dhammÜcariya*, three learning monks, three *PÜäipÜragPs*, three *pathamalats* and fourteen *Pathamanges*.

Emergence of PÜli University

Not very later after the University had founded, it was submitted to recognize as a university. The authorities came and examined the condition of the monastery. On the 7th waning of Tapotwe, 1320 ME (1.3.1959) they recognized as a university. So it emergence as a *PÜäi Pariyatti* University.

In the years 1320-1326 ME (1959-1964) it became the government university. However, the *SÜsanamaãâine* university endowed with the qualities of University. So it stands as a full-fledged University for 25 years. Within 25 years there appeared degree holders.

(1) 85 *SÜsanadhajadhammÜcariyas* holding 3 Texts for lecturers.

(2) 4 *SÜsanadhajasÝripavaradhammÜcariyas* with Myanmar Litreature distinction.

(3) 8 *SÜsanadhajasÝriparava PÜlipÜragþ* with PÜli distinction.

All together 97 monks could take the degree of lecturer. Therefore the fame of the *SÜsanamaãâine* was spread in the heart of the monks who took the *dhammÜcariya* examination.

Spreading the fame of the SÜsanamaãâine (SJJ, 32.)

During 25 years, not only dhammÜcariyas came out but also their passed 142 *Pathamagyis*, 247 *Pathamalats* and 330 *Pathamanges*. In addition, there assembled the AggamahÜkyaw and Pathamakyaw who got distinctions, the fame of the *SÜsanamaãâine PÜäi* University was spreading in the districts and townships. Therefore there was a motto "To pass the examination is to take the shelter of the Maãâine". According to this motto, the students who desire to pass the examination were building in the *SÜsanamaãâine* of Bago with endless coming. Now it was crowded that there was no room more.

Every year, since the fullmoon of Kason, the signboard was hanged written on it the entry list was closed. At the beginning of the raining season, after their examination, the student betterflies were crowed just like taking the sweet nectar over the arbour *Maãâine* University. It is to note that if one wants to stay at the *Maãâine* University, it is to investigate by oneself or later after the examination.

The Location of the SÜsanamaãâine University (SJJ, 32.)

The *SÜsanamaãâine* University was located at the top of the Panchankone quarter near the north end of *MaßgalÜ* door from the East face within the King Bayinnaung's city wall in Bago. The compound of the University was 5 acres and the half of the ground was level and the rest was on the city wall. It is 3 furlongs far away from the Shwemawdaw pagoda. If one wants to go to *Maãâine*, one has to go to the east stair of the pagoda leading to the mount of Shwehaãsa. When reached half of the stair, it will reach to the bus road. If he goes to the distance of two electric posts and continues to the bus road leading to the east. After three electric posts, he will reach the entrance of the *Maãâine* University. It is easy to be enquired.

If one wants to come by bus, it is to go along the Thanatpin road from the South entrance of the Shwemawdaw pagoda. When reached the east for 2 furlongs on the left corner of the road, it will be seen the fire extinguished station. It is to come

along the road of Panchankone leading due to north, U Khanti's stair will be seen. If coming into the bus road, it will be arrived at the entrance of the *Maããine* University.

Department of *Maããine Vinaya* recital (SJJ, 32.)

The *SÜsanamaããine Vinaya* recital had been held since 1341 ME (1980) allowed by the Sayadawgyis in-charge recognized for three days on the 7th, 8th and 9th waning of Nataw yearly with 500 monks. Within four years, it increased 2000 monks. They recited systematically and gracefully without jumping. All novices and monks had to recite it giving pleasantness to the donors. In coming and going for alms-food, they lined up. They took the food with bowl. As it was arranged to have reverence, the donors were very pleased and merits were achieved.

In the recital ceremony, regardless of junior or senior, they have to recital one text at least together. All offertories over divided among them. They were to recite 2 or 3 or 4 texts accordingly. There was no particular honour because of *NÜyaka* etc. They had to partake the food without alms-round as the donors came and offered the alms-food.

Noble meditation (SJJ, 38-39.)

Since 1339ME (1978), all monks of *Maããine* monastery had to take *SatipaááhÜna* meditation for ten days to accumulate merits (*pÜramÝ*) and to perform the practical (*paáipatti*) from the doctrinal (*pariyatti*) after their examination before going back home. As this meditation was observed by only monks, it was named the noble practice and held yearly.

The Buddha Himself said that if one had practised the *SatipaááhÜna* meditation, he would become Arahát (*P.T.S-76, The attainment of the last & highest stage of the Path.*) or *AnÜgam.* (*O,T,S-31. AnÜgÜmin (AnÜgÜn)-(a Never-Returner) designating one who has attain the 3rd stage out of four in the breaking o fthe bon (saãyojanas) which keep a man back from Arahantship. So near is the AnÜgÜmin to the goal, that after dead he will be reborn in one of the highest heaven and the obtain Arahantship, never returning to rebirth as a man.)*

Having accepted this speech, it would be the best for the one endowed with accumulated merits. According to this intention, as mentioned in the *Dhammapada* "one is not noble living a hundred years without seeing rising and passing. One is noble living even a single day if he sees rising and passing", the monks had to sit meditation.

Some thought that it need not to meditate as they were learning. It was an extra work. It was a sorrowful one.

Our *Maããine* monastery did not follow the method as a fashion. Since the beginning of the establishment of the monastery, it was to take the meditation practice in a proper time was prescribed in the basic constitution.

In this modern age, the learning of *Pariyatti* is strong but the practice for *Paáipatti* is weak. It seems there are many people who are speaking that it is enough if one is educated in learning but need not for practice. In fact monks and novices have not any knowledge of *Vinaya* and *Suttanta* enough, it would be heavy at heart for the Teachings of the Buddha and cycle of the rebirth. To overcome this difficulty, they were caused to revere the *Vinaya* and meditate the *SatipaááhÜna*. During ten days,

the lay men and women offered completely to them the dawn food and morning food and juice in the evening. In six years, there were 1390 monks meditated and 104 monks were to continue meditation in Yangon *MahÜsÝ* Centre.

***SÜsanamaãîne* Sub-monasteries** (SJJ, 41-42.)

1. *PajjotÜrÜma* monastery

Ven. *NÜgavaåsa*, Aung Chanthar quarter, Moneywar city, in this year, there were 250 monks had to observe rains- retreat.

2. Maung Htaung monastery

Ven. *Sucitta*, Ronegyi St, Moneywar city. There 15 monks had to take rains-retreat this year.

3. *SÜsanahitakÜrÝ* monastery

Ven. *JÜneyya*, Shauk Khar quarter, Moneywar city. There 10 monks had to take rains-retreat this year.

4. Ukkam Phayagyi *Pariyatti* monastery

Ven. Sayadaw *Lakkhaãa* and lecturer Ven. *Paããita*, Ven. *Jaáila*, Ven. *Issara*, Ukkam quarter, Thonekva city. There 60 monks had observed rains- retreat.

5. Kyaunggyisarthin Taik

Sayadaw *Tejavanta* and lecturer Ven. *PÜmokkha*, Kyautan township, Htantar village. There 25 monks had observed rains-retreat.

6. Masorein sarthin Taik

Sayadaw *Agginda*, Yangon district, Taikkyi city. Now there were 20 who had observed the two rains- retreat.

7. *SÜsanamaãîne* sarthin Taik

Ven. *SÝIÜnanda*, Ven. *Sadhammma*, Ven. *Visuddha*, *Windamera*, Yangon. There 25 monks had observed rains-retreat.

8. *SÜsanamaãîne* monastery

Ven. *ÉÜãika*, Htaw Hwak quarter, Thanlyin city. There 10 monks had observed rains-retreat.

9. Taung Swan, Shwekyin monastery

Ven. *Tejinda*, Ven, *ÉÜãavara*, Ye township, Acin village. There 25 monks had observed rains-retreat.

10. *MigadÜvun* monastery

Sayadaw *Sobhana*, Lceturer Ven, *Kittimanta*, Nyaunglaypin city. There 15 monks had observed rains-retreat.

11. *SÜsana* Aung Mye monastery

Ven, *MÜnitÜcÜra*, Ven, Sobhana, Minbu city. There 25 monks had observed rains-retreat.

12. *Brahmaso* monastery

Ven. *Pavara*, Bago district, Bhandarkone, Tarva. There 10 monks had observed rains-retreat.

13. Anauk Myo Htaut monastery

Ven, *Kuããala*, Hmankan, Bago city. There 25 monks had observed rains-retreat.

14. Ven, Kusala, Le Aye monastery

Lak Khut Kwin village, Daik U district. There 10 monks had observed rains-retreat.

15. Ven. SÝtala, *Dhammamaããine* monastery

Sankyo village, Thanatpin district. There 10 monks had observed rains-retreat.

Conclusion

The SÜsanamaããine PÜli University was founded in 1319 (1957) by the first abbot Ven. PaààÜjota (aggamahÜpaããita) together with his 37 pupils. Now it becomes 57 years old having over 500 to 600 students. It can hold 25 years Silver Jubilee and 50 years Gold Jubilee ceremonies. The current abbot is bhaddanta Saãvara (aggamahÜpaããita). The second abbot is Ven. PaààÜsÝha(aggamahÜpaããita). The administrator Sayadaw is Ven. Sirinda (aggamahÜpaããita). These four Sayadaws are not only well-versed in PÜli scriptures but also Rat, Tehtut, GÜthÜ and prose both in PÜli and Myanmar. They are also good teachers physically, verbally and spiriyually. So one cause of the monastery's success is the capacity of the successive Sayadaws. They can nurture the youth to become intellectuals and intelligentsias.

Another reason that makes the monastery develop is the administrative system. The disciplines for the monasteries and religious services are laid down systematically. Academic system is also very good that the students who want to pass the examination without effort can not stay in the monastery. The students who had followed the disciplines and studied the knowledge under the qualified Sayadaws become abbots just like the Sayadaws.

The SÜsanamaããine PÜli University has about 15 branch monasteries having students to some extent. Therefore the SÜsanamaããine PÜli University becomes prosperous within 60 years.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to express gratitude to Dr Min Aung, Adjunct-rector, Bago University and Professor Dr. Win Win Yi, Head of Oriental Studies Department, Bago University for constant encouragement and providing opportunity for publication of this paper.

References

UdÜnÜ PÜli, Suttantapáaka, Khuddaka NikÜya.

Buddhaghosa MahÜthera, Bhaddanta - *PÜRÜjikakaããda AáãhakathÜ.*

- Rhys Davids, T.W. (1966). *The Pali Text Society's Pali-English Dictionary*. London: Luza and Company, Ltd. London.
- SÜsanamaââine. (1983). *SÜsanamaââine Pariyatti PÜli University's Silver Jubilee Journal*. Bago: KÜyasukha Press.
- ZotipÜla, Ashin. (1983). *"SÜsanavaâsakkama VibhÜvani Text"*. Yangon: Soemoematesat Press, Myanmar.